

PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF A SENSE OF PATRIOTISM IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685316>

Annotation. This article analyzes the pedagogical features of the formation of a sense of patriotism in preschool children. Proposals were developed on the basis of the conclusions drawn.

Keywords. Supra-situational behavior, figurative understanding, affective feature, architectural monuments, sense of patriotism, cognitive feature, education of patriotism.

Taking into account the age characteristics of preschool children, the following points should be noted.

First, the upbringing of patriotism begins with love for the mother, parents, family, friends. This is the gradual formation of love, the thought of sympathy for another person, friendly affection. All these first childhood feelings will be the basis for the emergence of more complex social feelings. When we say patriotism in pre-school educational institutions, it is understood that love for the Motherland, the place where the child was born, the place where the grave of his ancestors is located, the upbringing of feelings of affection, which in the future becomes the foundation of loyalty, humility and loyalty to his country. . "Born", "parent", "relatives", "home", "my kindergarten, my street, village, city, province" -these and other words, phrases gradually develop the child's concept of step by step feeling.

Secondly, such phrases as "Love For The Motherland", "loyalty to the Motherland", "the House of fathers" indicate the origin of feelings of patriotism, high human feelings lie in early childhood experiences.

Thirdly, at every age of childhood there are basic ways of educating patriotism. At a small preschool age, this is an adult activity (example), which is a carrier of positive behavior, as well as Folk works-Children's rhymes, rhymes, songs, fairy tales, stories, children's magic. At 4-5 years old, a child gradually becomes aware of moral values and norms. During this period, the child can summarize his experience. There is a combination of ideas about the nature and methods of showing a positive attitude to adults and children. During this period, the teacher should focus the attention of the children on the methods of expressing the feelings of another person, he will teach them to "read" the feelings of the external appearance of animals and plants, motivate the child to give a worthy answer to the situation (help), sympathy, regret).

In addition to solving practical situations that arise in the life of each child, it is necessary to teach how to solve verbal logical problems ("if ..."what would you do if you were). Oral solutions of problems are interesting and useful for children of this age, they help the child to solve the current situation in an imaginary, imaginary, furry "safe" option, choose ways of solving them, proceeding from their own life experiences; develop imagination and logic.

In order to develop personal qualities and form a positive attitude to other children, there are joint actions with the people around them. During the period of joint work, the beginning of collective thought is born, the influence of society on the feelings of children.

From the fourth, patriotism is successfully carried out in the process of acquaintance with the people's culture. K. D. Ushinsky said that the form of education forms the culture of the nation, its well-being and spiritual direction. Fertile pedagogical developments, collected over the centuries in folklore, folk applied art, various types of folk crafts, classical works, works of masters of Russian painting, sculpture, architecture, are very close and understandable for preschool children. National culture and art create a conducive and conducive environment to reveal the level of development of national characteristics in a child with its potential. V.V.Zenkovsky points out: "if it is not absorbed into the basic feelings in which the spirit of the people lives, no one will be called the son of his people... However, we can argue that we can not achieve perfection beyond the national culture. it must be absorbed for the development of forces inherent in our soul."

From the fifth, the upbringing of patriotism is carried out by the upbringing of the national spiritual nature of the child. I. A. Ilyin wrote: "to educate the child and his character, first of all to reveal to him, his instincts, deep irrational sensitivity, diligence, the ability and happiness to love selflessly ... Homeland ... and it means believing in him. he's got it ...". The conditions created in the family and preschool institutions in order to raise the sense of respect for the labor skills and traditional products of our ancestors undoubtedly serve to educate the child as the patriot of his homeland. It is necessary to introduce children to the specific traditions and customs of the Russian people, to arouse interest in them and the desire to follow them, to get acquainted with the main moral values of the people (Russian people in this study), to help in the formation. positive attitude to traditions and the desire to observe them in everyday life.

From gold, the main element of patriotic education is nature. A special place is given to nature in the upbringing of a small patriot, because he constantly surrounds the child, enters his life early, is always understandable and open to the child. With representatives of the wild and wild, the child feels strong, important for them, because he can do something: to help, to be noble, to save someone's life. The child begins to understand that he is the creator and takes responsibility, thereby increasing his dignity.

In preschool children, social emotions and motivations develop. How they are formed at the beginning of a child's life depends on his further development. The growth line (self-development) associated with the "ilgish" in the physical and mental development of the child by the nature of praise or organization of children's activities by adults has a "curved" appearance. Here shaxsiyat can appear, any stage of development is accompanied by the possibility of manifestation and consolidation of negative neoplasms.

Self-awareness in preschool childhood to significant changes threeraydi (OBR-the image of "I" as a cognitive subject). Affektiv when speaking on the side, the attitude of a person to himself is understood, and on the cognitive side he is understood to manifest or know himself. The source of

the image of "I" in preschool children is the experience of independent work and communication with adults and peers. The first has a significant impact on the formation of a cognitive attitude towards oneself, the second is affective.

The main achievement in preschool is a clear, confident, generally emotional and positive self-esteem.

At the preschool age, the child's moral and moral foundations, his emotional feelings, thinking, social adaptations are formed, the process of self-realization begins in the world around him. This part of human life has a very beneficial effect on the child emotionally and psychologically, because the images of his perception are very bright and strong, so they are stored in memory for a long time, sometimes lifelong, and this is important in the upbringing of patriotism.

Each age stage includes its own characteristics in the upbringing of patriotism. For seven years, children experience three main periods of development, each of which is characterized by a certain stage in the direction of universal values and new opportunities for learning, changing and mastering the world. These periods of life are limited to a number of possible achievements in the psychophysiological development of a preschool child. Each previous cycle creates prerequisites for the next cycle, and it is impossible to rearrange them in time and space.

A preschool child begins to put himself on the level of other people, to understand what is happening from their position, their motivations and actions, to independently build the future result of effective activity. At this age, the child must take into account the opportunities for the active formation and upbringing of patriotism, the development of a sense of sympathy for others and an emotionally effective relationship with them.

The leading feature of the child psyche is imitation. Children imitate both good and bad, they are easily inclined to external influence because critical thinking has not yet developed sufficiently. An adult preschool child gets rid of the "global imitation" of adults, characteristic of the early stage, can to some extent resist the will of another person; cognitive methods are developed, in particular, the ability to change reality by imagination, voluntary (initiative, the ability to force oneself to be uninteresting) and emotional (self-expression of feelings) - self-control. The child turns out to be capable of supra-situational (going beyond the initial requirements) behavior. Proceeding from this, we can conclude that one of the important ways of educating patriotism is a personal example of an adult (teacher, parent and other adult around the child), his whole way of life.

An example of an adult and especially close to him is of great importance in the upbringing of a large preschool child in the spirit of patriotism. Consequently, the task of the teacher, relying on the predisposition of the child to imitation, is to impregnate him with skills and skills, creative work without them is difficult, to educate his independence, his activity in the application of these knowledge and skills. also critical thinking and the formation of a targeted direction. The basis of the creative activity of the preschool child is formed, which is manifested in the development of

the ability to create and implement projects, in the ability to harmonize their knowledge and conclusions, in the sincere return of their feelings.

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